

SUMMARY - IRAMUTEQ Installation

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1. PREREQUISITES

- Internet connection;
- Computer with Windows system;
- Administrator rights.

2. INSTALL R

- Access: <https://cran.r-project.org/bin/windows/base>
- Download the installer (e.g., R-4.4.0-win.exe);
- Run the file and click "Next".

3. INSTALL IRAMUTEQ

- Access: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/iramuteq>
- Download the installer (IramuteqSetup.exe);
- Run the file and complete the installation.

4. FIRST EXECUTION

- Upon opening, the program synchronizes with R;
- Automatically installs the necessary libraries.

5. POSSIBLE PROBLEMS

- IRaMuTeQ does not open? Check if R is installed.

- Library error? Try running:

```
=install.packages("tm")
```

```
=install.packages("slam")
```

SUMMARY - IRAMUTEQ Usage

1. PREPARE THE CORPUS

- Use Notepad and save as .txt with UTF-8 encoding.

Structure:

```
**** *Corpus_1
```

Text from the first source.

*****Corpus_2

Text from the second source.

2. IMPORTING THE CORPUS

-Menu: File -> Open a text corpus

-Choose the .txt file, UTF-8 encoding, language: Portuguese

3. TYPES OF ANALYSIS

-Statistics: word frequency

-Specificities and CFA (Factorial Correspondence Analysis): correlation between words and variables

-DHC (Descending Hierarchical Classification): classification of textual segments

-Similitude Analysis: connections between words

-Word Cloud: visualization of most frequent words

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

-Use lemmatization;

-Save results in a separate folder;

-For DHC (Descending Hierarchical Classification), use up to 10 classes;

-Use "communities" in similitude for better visualization.